

Linking Star Formation and Black Hole Accretion in galaxies

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Outline

- ❑ Observational evidences of galaxies co-evolving with their nuclear activity
- ❑ Secular processes regulating SFR and BHAR
- ❑ Implication for local scaling relations
- ❑ The role of starbursts/mergers

AGN and SB co-exist in galaxies at all redshifts

- $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ indicates a tight link between BH and galaxy growth
- Global SF and BH growth follows same trends
- Molecular outflows (ubiquitous?)

How are BH and galaxy growths linked?

Connection of star formation to stellar mass keeps up to very high- z

90% of the SFRD is assembled on the MS at $z=2$ (Elbaz+11, Rodighiero+11)

An evolutionary scenario driven by quenching mechanisms?

Secular processes are probably responsible for both SFR and SMBH growth in a large majority of galaxies displaying moderate nuclear activity (Cisternas 2011, Kocevski 2012).

The role of violent mergers is still considered an important triggering mechanism for BH growth (i.e. AGN activity), in particular in very luminous QSO (Hopkins 2008, Treister 2012).

The classical merger/QSO paradigm (Hopkins+08)

However, it is now clear that processes other than galaxy mergers, such as gas turbulence or disk instabilities, play an important role in triggering BHAR (Bournaud et al. 2012).

Bournaud et al. (2011)

Dai+15

Many studies find no clear correlation between instantaneous BH growth and SF for individual galaxies of moderate X-ray luminosities (Silverman+09, Shao+10, Mullaney et al. 2012a, Azadi et al. 2014).

Azadi+14

galaxies can switch between an "inactive" state (appearing as normal galaxy) and a bright AGN state over timescales of \sim Myr or less

AGN duty cycle: AGN vary significantly, from hours to Myr \rightarrow far shorter than the typical timescale for SF (100 Myr)

- \rightarrow Average BHAR: select on a highly transient event.
- \rightarrow Average SFR: select on a more stable event

Average BH growth in SF galaxies: the AGN MS

(Average over AGN duty cycles using X-ray stacking)

SAMPLE: COSMOS2015 catalog (Laigle+15) and Chandra-Legacy (Civano+15)

PROCEDURE: Stacking on bins of redshifts and stellar masses for three independent populations:

1. Normal star-forming (colour selection)
2. Passive galaxies (colour selection)
3. Starbursts (Herschel sources $x_{4>MS}$)

Stack far-IR (PACS/Herschel) \rightarrow average SFR

Stack X-ray (Chandra) \rightarrow average BHAR

$$\text{BHAR}(M_*, z) = \frac{(1 - \epsilon) \cdot L_{\text{bol}}(M_*, z)}{\epsilon c^2}$$

Star forming galaxies

Evolution of SFR & BHAR
versus stellar mass
for normal star-forming
galaxies:
almost linear relations
(bending apart...)

← stacked L_x :
average of detections and
undetected, subtracted for
SFR contribution

$$\log(\text{BHAR}/\text{SFR}) = K + 0.45 * \log(M_*)$$

$$M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_*^{1.45}$$

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Star forming galaxies

Evolution of SFR & BHAR versus stellar mass for normal star-forming galaxies:

IS

nd
l for

(M_*)

Yang+17

Quiescent galaxies

Evolution of SFR & BHAR
versus stellar mass
for quiescent galaxies
flatter relations
(in particular at higher z)

High-z passive massive galaxies follow the local scaling relation between M^* and M_{BH}

$$\log(\text{BHAR}/\text{SFR})=K$$

$$M_{\text{BH}} = 10^{-3} M_*$$

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Starburst galaxies

Evolution of SFR & BHAR
versus stellar mass
for starbursts

**Lx independent of M_* and
slightly evolving with z**

SB have a constant ratio but
smaller than quenched sources
(x2-x10)

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First question we can answer:
where's the bulk of BH masses formed at
the peak of the cosmic SFRD?

Given the number densities and average L_x of
the various population, we argue that

The bulk (80%) of the accretion density of the
Universe is associated with normal star-forming
gals.

(Rodighiero+15)

if

$$M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_*^{1.45}$$

$$s\text{BHAR} = \frac{\text{BHAR}}{M_{\text{BH}}} \quad s\text{SFR} = \frac{\text{SFR}}{M_*}$$

Star forming galaxies

- ◆ Decrease with cosmic time
- ◆ Downsizing
- ◆ Mass-doubling timescale of M_{BH} slightly shorter than that of M_{*}

Quiescent galaxies

- ◆ Decrease with cosmic time
- ◆ Downsizing
- ◆ Average lower (x15-20) sBHAR and sSFR with respect to star-forming*

Starburst galaxies

- ◆ sBHAR constant with cosmic time (no evolution)
- ◆ Downsizing?

SUMMARY .I

- We found a robust BHAR- M_* correlation for normal star-forming galaxies up to $z=3.5$: on average, BH growth mimics galaxy growth in MS.
- Suggestion that it is the same underlying physics (gas reservoirs?) that drive SF and BH growth, to produce the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ correlation.
- M_{bh}/M_* not constant with mass (scales as $M_*^{1.45}$): BHs accrete more mass with respect to their host galaxies at the high mass.
- The bulk of the accretion density of the Universe is associated with normal star-forming at $z=2$ (peak of cosmic co-evolutions).
 - Downsizing evidences for both SF and BH accretion.

The $M_{\text{BH}} - M_{\text{STAR}}$ relation is mostly a consequence of the $M_{\text{BH}} - \sigma$ and $\sigma - M_{\text{STAR}}$ relations, and is heavily biased by up to a factor of 50 at small masses.

Shankar+16
and Reines&Volonteri 2015

BH mass fractions as a function of stellar mass: comparing to local scaling relations

SUMMARY .II

1. Massive quenched galaxies have already assembled their SMBH by $z=2$, through early and fast accretion processes.
2. Intermediate mass star-forming galaxies are dominated by secular evolution, probably guided by the continuous availability of gas reservoirs that feed both SFR and BHAR.
3. Merger driven starbursts are luminous events (both in X-ray and far-IR) but do not contribute significantly to the build up of local BH relations (see also Simmons+17).

The role of starbursts/mergers

Testing the classical merger-BH/QSO sequence through morphology and gas masses

Selection of starbursts in COSMOS

Herschel starbursts: UV-to-subMM SED fitting with SED3D (Berta et al. 2014). Dusty torus contribution to IR luminosity → AGN and SFR dominated starbursts

- 25% of starbursts are classified as AGN dominated
- few X-ray AGNs among starbursts (8, with 6 in our AGN class)

Look for ALMA statistical continuum detection of SB:
a census of gas (...dust) masses to check
for potential AGN feedback effects (13 already in the archive!)

HST morphology: Star Formation dominated Starbursts

3"x3"

Totally optically obscured

See J. Silverman's talk for this guy!

Detected SFR-SB in ALMA band 8 available in the archive

HST morphology: AGN dominated Starbursts

Compact/nuclear morphology

3"x3"

midz_cell8_102386

midz_cell10_264521

z12_55

midz_cell12_274938

midz_cell8_254150

dusty blue nuggets? (see Avishai's talk)

AGN feedback signatures?

Gas masses from empirical calibration of 850 μ m
dust continuum (*Scoville+16*)

Average gas mass AGN = $2 \pm 0.6 \times 10^{10} M_{\text{sun}}$

Average gas mass SFR = $5 \pm 1.5 \times 10^{10} M_{\text{sun}}$

→ Significant x2.5 factor larger gas masses in
SFR dominated Starbursts

Average gas fraction AGN = $30 \pm 9 \%$

Average gas fraction SFR = $40 \pm 4 \%$

→ Marginal 10% factor larger gas fractions in
SFR dominated Starbursts

Main sequence: AGNs are on average hosted in galaxies much more gas rich than inactive galaxies.

SUMMARY .III

- **Dusty Starbursts are an ideal place to look for merger induced AGN activity, and potential effects of feedback**
- **SB dominated by an obscured AGN component have more regular and compact morphology**
- **SB dominated by an obscured AGN component have lower gas masses (but this has to be confirmed with larger samples and independent gas mass measurements)**

It's Coffee Time!

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!